

Predictors of Criminologist Licensure Examination Performance

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Date Submitted:

January 29, 2026

Date Accepted:

February 27, 2026

Date Published:

March 10, 2026

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.18964178

ABSTRACT

One of the most difficult obstacles a graduate must overcome in order to obtain a license for his or her profession is the Licensure Examination. This study aimed to determine the predictors or factors that influence Criminology students' performance in the Criminologist licensure examination. The study utilized descriptive-correlational research design. The respondents of the study were the 112 Criminology graduates from a private institution in Cagayan de Oro City who took the Criminologist Licensure Examination in the years 2019 (June & November), 2021 (December) and 2023 (August). They were chosen using purposive sampling. Secondary data generated from the system were used to gather the needed information for the study. Data

were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation, Pearson product – Moment Correlation Coefficient and Regression Analysis. Most of the respondents were very satisfactory in their general weighted averages (GWA), and they also performed very satisfactorily during their on-the-job training. However, they perform poorly in their comprehensive exam. Nevertheless, majority of the respondents' passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE). Analyses examining the relationship between respondents' general weighted averages in BS Criminology subjects and their CLE performance revealed a moderate positive correlation indicating that as GWAs increase, CLE performance tends to improve significantly. Similarly, strong positive correlations were found between performance in On-the-Job Training (OJT) and CLE results, as well as between results on comprehensive exams and CLE performance, underscoring the predictive value of both practical training and academic assessments. Furthermore, both the Comprehensive Examination Score and OJT Grade emerged as significant predictors of Criminology graduates' performance in Criminologist Licensure Examination. In conclusion, both the scores from the Comprehensive Examination and the On-the-Job Training (OJT) Grade are important indicators of Criminology graduates' success in the Criminologist Licensure Examination. As part of the recommendation, in order to enhance students' performance, administrators must ensure that instructors overseeing OJT and comprehensive examination subjects possess the necessary expertise and teaching abilities for effective instruction delivery.

Keywords: *Criminologist licensure examination, on the job training, comprehensive examination teachers' performance, criminology graduates.*

INTRODUCTION

The quality of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines can be determined in a number of ways. The results of graduates of HEIs in state licensing exams are one concrete indicator that is frequently used throughout the nation (Padua, 2003). Licensure Examinations are one of the greatest challenges a graduate must overcome to obtain a license for his or her profession. The regulating body must feel confident in issuing a license once a graduate has passed a licensing exam in order to reassure the public that the licensee is at least minimally qualified to practice at the time of initial licensure. The examination is intended to prove the graduates' knowledge, development, and readiness for a particular position. Additionally, a school's quality of education is determined by how well its graduates perform on the licensure examination, which ultimately ensures that the graduate will be able to apply what they have learned effectively and efficiently in their chosen profession or career. (Hertz & Chinn, 2000). Criminology, like other academic fields, draws on a range of theoretical stances that have emerged and evolved over time. Naturally, these viewpoints, as well as the theories, notions, agendas, and customs they are connected with, should be familiar to criminology students (Tierney, 2009).

A person who is a holder of a Bachelor's Degree in Criminology is required to pass the Criminologist Licensure Examination administered by the Professional Regulation Commission of the Philippines to be regarded as Registered Criminologist in order for such to be given full authority to practice the said profession. The Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE) was introduced in 1972 by Republic Act No. 6506. The examination was intended to standardize the country's criminology profession. The Criminology Board Examination's areas of concentration are also provided by this act (Noderama, 2020). RA 6506 was then amended by RA 11131 the Philippine Criminology Profession Act of 2018 which stipulates that anyone who wishes to practice criminology must pass the Criminologists Licensure Examinations (CLE) given by the Professional Regulation Commission's (PRC) Professional Regulatory Board of Criminology. RA 11131 governs criminologists' examination, registration, and licensure; the supervision, control, and regulation of criminology practice; the standardization and regulation of criminology education; the development of criminologists' professional competence; and the integration of all professional criminology groups. Under RA 11131, in order to pass the criminology licensure examination, a candidate must have a weighted average rating of 75 percent with no grade less than 60 percent in any subject. It is also required to deliver professional criminologist oaths to successful examinees in the criminology licensure examination.

In the recent Licensure Examination for Criminologists, administered by the Board of Criminology last April 2023 in 30 testing venues all over the Philippines, only 4,139 passed out of 13,000 examinees, according to the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC). On August 25-27, 2023, another Criminology board exam was conducted at several testing centers located in the NCR, Baguio, Butuan, Cagayan de Oro, Calapan (Oriental Mindoro), Cebu, Davao, Iloilo, Koronadal, Legazpi, Lucena, Pagadian, San Fernando (Pampanga), Tacloban, Tuguegarao, Zamboanga, Antique, Bacolod, Bohol, Cauayan (Isabela), Dumaguete, Ilocos Norte, Ilocos Sur, Kidapawan, Occidental Mindoro, Naga, and Palawan and just recently result was

released, out of 17,576 applicants only 5,743 were found to have passed the Licensure Examination for Criminologists (PRC, 2023).

Given the examination result, all criminology faculty members should carefully and thoroughly evaluate the subjects included in the professional components of the BS Criminology curriculum vis-à-vis competencies for each subject area to ensure that the curriculum for BS Criminology is keeping up with changes in the Criminology Education curriculum (Brigman & Campbell, 2003). The key to improving the preparation, licensure, certification, and ongoing development processes in place now is to change the standards for teaching learning. Such guidelines can improve a project's focus and clarity on a group of presently disconnected and frequently disorganized activities. Without a doubt, for students to succeed they should expect their teachers to uphold the same high standards. The performance of the student in the Criminologist Licensure Examination may be impacted by a variety of things. Review classes that the examinees enrolled in after graduation are one of those factors, analysis indicates that the issues included in the review have a high degree of relevance and difficulty (Quiambao, et al, 2015).

Every criminology graduate can access a variety of prospects in numerous sectors by passing the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE). As a result, applicant success in this particular licensure exam is accorded top priority. This justification encourages several criminology departments at universities, colleges, and other institutions to design and implement suitable curricula that meet their educational goals and, more crucially, get a high CLE performance grade.

The study aims to determine the predictors or factors that influence Criminology students' performance in the Criminologist licensure examination to facilitate the improvements in education and preparation of the students in their board examination. The study aimed to determine the Criminology graduates general weighted average, on-the-job training performance and comprehensive examination performance. This also determined the significant relationship between the GWA, OJT performance, and comprehensive examination performance when compared to their Criminologist Licensure examination performance. This study played a vital role in shaping the future of Criminology education and professional practice. It contributes to the ongoing improvement of educational programs, the success of aspiring professionals, and the overall integrity and effectiveness of the Criminology profession. The Professional Criminologist Association in the Philippines with the Professional Regulation Commission faces a big challenge in making sure that students do well on their Criminologist Licensure Examination. Determining the predictors in CLE performance is important in improving the education and supporting students' success in the Criminologist Licensure Examination.

METHODS

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design, a method in which the researcher examines the statistical association between two or more variables without manipulating them. This design aims to determine whether, and to what extent, changes in one variable are correlated with changes in another. It does not establish causation but focuses on observing variables as they naturally occur.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in a non-sectarian private institution in Cagayan de Oro, Philippines, established in 1971. The institution is a stock corporation registered with the Securities and Exchange Commission and operates under the authority of the Department of Education for elementary and secondary programs, and the Commission on Higher Education for tertiary, graduate, and postgraduate programs. Cagayan de Oro, also known as the “City of Golden Friendship,” is a first-class city in Northern Mindanao and the capital of Misamis Oriental province. It is known for its white rapids, warm and friendly people, and strategic location as the “Gateway to Northern Mindanao.”

Respondents of the Study

The respondents were graduates of this private institution who took the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE) in June and November 2019, December 2021, and August 2023, administered by the Board of Criminology of the Professional Regulation Commission. Both first-time and repeat examinees were included, with a total of 112 respondents. These three batches were chosen because no CLE was conducted in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the institution had no takers in 2022 as students opted for longer preparation time and due to the implementation of RA 11131.

Data Sources and Data Collection

Secondary data were utilized in this study, collected from the private institution. Data included respondents’ general weighted average in BS Criminology subjects, performance in on-the-job training (OJT), performance in comprehensive examinations, and performance in the CLE. The study also analyzed the significant relationships between students’ GPAs, OJT performance, comprehensive exam performance, and their CLE results, as well as predictors of Criminology graduates’ performance in the licensure examination.

Permission to conduct the study was first sought from the Dean of the Graduate School. Upon approval, the researcher, who is employed at the same institution, also requested permission from the College Dean to access the necessary data. After receiving approval, the researcher ensured that all data collected were accurate and complete before analysis and tabulation.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were strictly observed. The office of the Dean and faculty were fully informed about the study's objectives and purpose. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed that they could withdraw at any time without consequences. All data collected were kept confidential, and a debriefing was provided after the study to explain how participants' contributions supported the research objectives.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Data analysis employed mean and standard deviation to determine student performance, Pearson Product–Moment Correlation Coefficient to examine the relationship between academic and CLE performance, and regression analysis to identify factors predicting graduates' performance in the CLE.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: *Respondents General Weighted Average in BS in Criminology Subjects*

Grade Point Average in BS in Criminology Subjects	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	3	2.68
Very Satisfactory	37	33.04
Satisfactory	30	26.79
Fair	26	23.21
Poor	8	7.14
Very Poor	8	7.14
Total	112	100.00

Table 1 displays the distribution of respondents' general weighted average in Bachelor of Science in Criminology subjects. GWA are categorized into Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fair, Poor, and Very Poor.

According to the data, most of the respondents 37 (33.04%) obtained a very satisfactory general weighted average. Which was followed by satisfaction with 30 respondents (26.79%). General weighted average of outstanding, fair, and poor each have frequencies ranging from 3 to 26, representing 2.68% to 23.21% of the total respectively. Additionally, there are 8 respondents (7.14%) in both the poor and very poor categories.

This implies that knowing how student performance is distributed can help educators and administrator pinpoint regions that might require more resources or attention. For example, if a sizable

portion of students consistently receive lower grades, this could be an indicator of problems with the course material or teaching methods that need to be changed. Recognizing the distribution of GWAs can also inspire students to aim for greater academic success by giving them insight into the competitive atmosphere within their program. Results highlight the significance of ongoing assessment and development in curriculum design and pedagogy for legislators and stakeholders in the field of Criminology education. This will help to guarantee that students have the information and abilities needed for success in their future careers. The general weighted average or the general grade point average is a statistical measure that considers differences in the value or weight of distinct components in a dataset. In educational institutions, it is widely used to determine a student's overall performance by assigning varying weights to grades based on the credit hours or units associated with each course. This method presents a more nuanced picture of academic accomplishment than a simple average since it considers the relative importance of courses with varied complexities or credit values (Akhilesh Ganti, 2023).

The best predictor of academic performance is still the general weighted average (GWA), calculated on an ordinal scale. Students are generally classified as high, average, or low achievers depending on their GWA (Magpily & Mercado, 2014). A variety of circumstances might impact a student's academic achievement, both within and outside of school. According to Julio and Liwag (2016), student factors include family, school, and peer factors.

This implies that the General Weighted Average (GWA) distribution of students enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Criminology courses emphasizes the significance of GWA in predicting success on board exams. Since most students receive very satisfactory GWAs, educators are able to pinpoint problem areas and inspire students to perform at their best. This highlights how important it is to continuously review students and improve the curriculum in order to make sure they are ready for employment. The GWA provides a comprehensive evaluation of academic performance by taking into consideration differences in the weight of various components. The GWA, which ranks students according to their success levels, is still the most accurate indicator of performance, even in the face of several influencing variables. To improve overall results, specific interventions and enhancements in Criminology education can be informed by an understanding of and application of GWA distribution.

Table 2: *Respondents Performance in their OJT*

Academic Performance in Professional Subjects	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	15	13.39
Very Satisfactory	57	50.89
Satisfactory	22	19.64
Fair	18	16.07
Poor	-	-
Very Poor	-	-
Total	112	100.00

Table 2 presents the distribution of respondents' performance during their On-the- Job Training (OJT), categorized by their academic performance in professional subjects. According to the data, the most common performance level during OJT is very satisfactory, with 57 respondents accounting for 50.89% of the total. This was followed by satisfactory with 22 respondents (19.64%) and outstanding with 15 respondents (13.39%). Additionally, there are 18 respondents (16.07%) categorized as having "Fair" performance during OJT, while no respondents fall into the poor or very poor categories.

It is evident on the data that a majority of respondents performed well or satisfactorily during their OJT, as indicated by the high frequencies in the very satisfactory and satisfactory categories. However, there is a smaller proportion of respondents classified as having outstanding performance, suggesting that while many students performed adequately during their OJT, fewer achieved exceptional results.

Data implies firstly, for educational institutions offering programs with OJT components, understanding the distribution of student performance can help in assessing the effectiveness of OJT placements and identifying areas for improvement in training or support mechanisms for students. Moreover, for students, recognizing the distribution of performance levels during OJT can provide insights into the expectations and standards of employers in their field, motivating them to strive for higher levels of proficiency and professionalism. Additionally, for law enforcement agencies, these findings underscore the importance of providing adequate support and mentorship to students during their OJT to ensure that they are equipped with the skills and experience necessary for success in their future careers. Overall, by leveraging these insights, educational institutions, students, and law enforcement agencies can collaboratively work towards enhancing the quality and impact of OJT experiences in professional development.

The internship program offers the tasks, organizational environment, and culture needed for hands-on learning in authentic settings. As a result, it reinforces the knowledge that the students have learned in the four corners of the room regarding the practical application of many disciplines in criminalistics and crime detection and investigation.

On-The-Job Training (OJT) programs expose students to work in the field they have chosen and prepare them once they leave the university or college they have attended. Furthermore, OJT is an essential component of the academic programs at universities such as the NEUST because they give undergraduate students the chance to integrate work-related knowledge and experience into their formal education by participating in planned, supervised work in a real-world professional setting. The Commission on Higher Education requires all programs to have an internship because the programs will enable students to investigate the connections between the knowledge and abilities they learned in college and the skills needed in the workplace (Aydinan, 2019).

A significant portion of Criminology students' education involves on-the-job training. By providing practical experience and skill development both necessary for a successful career in the criminal justice

system it augments academic learning. If criminology students can apply what they have learned in the classroom to real-world settings, acquire practical abilities, and concentrate on specific areas, they will be prepared for the demands of their future professions. On-the-job training for Criminology students eventually results in a more comprehensive education and improved preparedness to contribute to their field, despite potential challenges (Anoyo et.al, 2015).

One of the primary benefits of on-the-job training is the opportunity to gain real- world experience and abilities. Students can gain insight into the everyday operations of a number of criminal justice institutions as well as their such as law enforcement agencies, probation offices, and correctional facilities, by seeing and learning from experienced experts. Giving them real-world duties and responsibilities helps them learn the subtleties of the job, build critical thinking skills, and improve their problem-solving ability (Anoyo et al, 2015).

This implies that the distribution of students' performance during On-the-Job Training (OJT) emphasizes how important it is for predicting success on board exams. Given that the majority of students receive satisfactory or very satisfactory grades, their practical skills are clearly well-established. Less exceptional performers, meanwhile, point to potential for development. These suggest that educational institutions ought to assess the value of OJT and improve their support systems. Comprehending OJT standards inspires pupils to pursue professional development. By integrating theory and practice, on- the-job training (OJT) gives students practical experience and improves their preparedness for the Criminologist Licensure Examination. In conclusion, OJT performance is essential for Criminology students to prepare for their future jobs, highlighting the value of real- world experience in the learning process.

Table 3: *Respondents Performance in Comprehensive Examination*

Academic Performance in Professional Subjects	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	-	-
Very Satisfactory	-	-
Satisfactory	-	-
Fair	-	-
Poor	18	16.07
Very Poor	94	83.93
Total	112	100.00

Table 3 illustrates the distribution of respondents' performance levels in comprehensive examination. According to the data, the majority of respondents, accounting for 94 individuals (83.93%), were assessed as having very poor performance. There were also 18 respondents (16.07%) who obtained a poor performance. However, no respondents were rated as having outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, or fair performance in the comprehensive examination.

Data reveal a concerning trend wherein a significant proportion of respondents were appraised as having poor or very poor performance levels. This suggests potential gaps in the acquisition or application of skills and knowledge required for professional practice. Such a scenario may indicate deficiencies in the educational program's effectiveness in preparing students for real-world challenges or shortcomings in the assessment methods used to evaluate competency.

Data implies that the majority of respondents performed so poorly on the comprehensive exam might indicate the need for better preparation strategies among them. Institutions should as well consider providing study materials, and review sessions to help students prepare in their comprehensive examinations.

Comprehensive examinations are similar to board exams, with the exception that they are given in schools. The format of the examination and the complexity of the question papers are often similar to those of real board exams. While some might argue that taking a comprehensive exam prior to the boards is ineffective, its main objective is to assist students in assessing their level of preparation and familiarizing themselves with the kinds of questions that will be on the boards. Comprehensive examinations are used to assess how well they perform. Using the Comprehensive examinations, students can monitor their development. The blueprints for boards are found in the Comprehensive examinations questions (Chauhan, 2019).

Comprehensive examinations give students an excellent means of determining how prepared they are. It is a serious error to fail the comprehensive tests because they are an excellent means of evaluating one's preparedness for the board exam (Patelkhana, 2019). According to Dotado-Maderazo and Ercia's (2017) research, a simulated board could be useful in assessing a graduate's strengths and weaknesses before they finish the board test. Comprehensive examinations could provide an overview of the subjects that students are concentrating on in order to improve the areas where they appear to be receiving low grades.

This implies that the distribution of performance levels in the Comprehensive Examination highlights its importance in predicting board examination success. With a significant majority receiving poor or very poor ratings, there are evident gaps in skills and knowledge crucial for professional practice. This underscores the need for better preparation strategies and support mechanisms. Comprehensive examinations serve as valuable tools for assessing readiness and identifying areas for improvement, making them essential for students' academic journey toward success in board exams and professional practice.

Table 4: *Respondents' Performance in the Criminology Licensure Examination*

Performance	M	SD
<i>Criminal JurisPrudence</i>		
Passed	89	79.46
Failed	23	20.54
<i>Law Enforcement Administration</i>		
Passed	100	89.29
Failed	12	10.71
<i>Crime Detection and Investigation</i>		
Passed	93	83.04
Failed	19	16.96
<i>Forensic Science</i>		
Passed	104	92.86
Failed	8	7.14
<i>Correctional Administration</i>		
Passed	99	88.39
Failed	13	11.61
<i>Criminology</i>		
Passed	96	85.71
Failed	16	14.29
Overall Performance		
Passed	97	86.61
Failed	15	13.39

Scale: 75-100 (Passed); 74 and below (Failed)

Table 4 presents the comprehensive overview of Criminology graduates' performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE) across various specializations. Examining the "Passed" category reveals encouraging results. Notably, the graduates exhibited strong performance across all subjects, with mean scores ranging from 89 to 104. Criminal Jurisprudence, Law Enforcement Administration, Crime Detection and Investigation, Forensic Science, Correctional Administration, and Criminology all recorded high mean scores, signifying a robust understanding of their respective domains. The overall performance, reflecting a mean score of 97, further underscores the overall excellence of Criminology graduates in the CLE.

On the other hand, the analysis of the "Failed" category sheds light on areas where improvement may be needed. While the number of failures is relatively low across all subjects, ranging from 8 to 23, the

standard deviations reveal varying degrees of spread in the performance. The subjects with higher standard deviations, such as Criminal Jurisprudence (20.54) and Crime Detection and Investigation (16.96), indicate greater variability in scores among those who did not pass. This highlights potential challenges and areas of concern that merit closer examination and targeted interventions to address specific weaknesses and ensure a more consistent level of proficiency among Criminology graduates. Overall, the findings underscore the strengths of Criminology education while signaling opportunities for focused improvements to enhance overall success rates in the Criminologist Licensure Examination.

Overall, Criminology graduates demonstrated strong performance across various subjects, including Criminal Jurisprudence, Law Enforcement Administration, Crime Detection and Investigation, Forensic Science, Correctional Administration, and their specialization. Notably, graduates exhibited high levels of competency in Forensic Science, as evidenced by consistently high mean scores and low standard deviations, indicating a uniform understanding of the subject matter. However, some variability in performance was observed in other subjects, suggesting the need for further investigation into factors contributing to differences in scores and potential areas for targeted interventions to improve performance consistency. Despite variations, the overall performance in the Criminology Licensure Examination (CLE) was commendable, emphasizing the need for continued support and development initiatives to address any disparities in performance across graduates.

In previous years of the Criminologist Licensure Examination, the stated private institutions' takers were able to have a solid performance in the board examinations, with the overall result exceeding the national passing %. June 2019. The passing percentage of such institutions for first takers was 93.33%, exceeding the national passing percentage of 38.47%. This was followed by November 2019, which obtained a passing percentage of 87.50% for first takers while the national passing percentage was 44.11%, December 2021 first takers of the said institutions obtained a passing percentage of 88.89% and the national passing percentage was 34.19%, and the most recent August 2023 examination first takers of the said institutions obtained a passing percentage of 87.50% which was higher than the national passing percentage of 32.68%.

The licensure exam is essential for ascertaining a performance of the school in terms of the standard of instruction it offers. This examination must be passed in order to practice a certain profession. It is necessary in order to become an acknowledged authority in a particular profession (Binayao and Dales, 2020). Actual results in the Philippine Criminologist Licensure Exams are the most reliable measure of a student's performance in the Criminology bachelor's program the abilities, capabilities, and knowledge that are declared to represent the anticipated results of a quality-certified HEI could be quantified in part by these evaluations (Padua, 2012).

The Criminology students' licensure examination holds significant implications for both individual professionals and the broader field of criminology. On an individual level, successfully passing the licensure examination ensures that criminology graduates possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and competence

to practice their profession effectively, contributing to the overall competence and professionalism within the field. This examination serves as a gateway, granting licensed criminologists' access to various employment opportunities in both the private and public sectors. Moreover, the licensure examination plays a critical role in maintaining high standards within the criminology profession, as it serves as a benchmark for evaluating core competencies and ensuring that practitioners meet established criteria. Thus, the examination not only validates individual capabilities but also upholds the quality and integrity of the criminology profession as a whole, reinforcing its importance in promoting excellence and accountability within the field (Wallenfeldt & McCudden, 2020).

Numerous studies conducted in the Philippines have looked at the factors that influence a students' performance in licensure exams. Grade point average (GPA), success on comprehensive exams or in-house evaluations, final internship (OJT) grades, and the goals, attitudes, and study habits of the students are some of these factors (Constantino et al., 2014).

This implies that the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE) serves as a crucial assessment of Criminology graduates' competence and readiness for professional practice. Successful performance in the CLE validates graduates' knowledge and skills, enabling them to pursue various career opportunities. Moreover, the examination maintains high standards within the field, ensuring practitioners meet established criteria for competency and professionalism. Factors influencing students' performance in licensure exams, such as GPA and internship grades, highlight the importance of effective preparation strategies. Overall, the CLE plays a vital role in upholding the quality and integrity of the criminology profession, emphasizing the need for continuous assessment and targeted interventions to enhance graduates' readiness for professional practice.

Table 5: *Significant Relationship between Respondents' Grade Weighted Average in BS Criminology Subjects and their Performance in the Criminology Licensure Examination*

Grade Point Average	r value	p value	Decision
	0.425**	0.000	Reject Ho

Ho: There is no significant relationship between respondents' grade weighted average in BS Criminology subjects and their performance in the Criminology Licensure examination.

*Legend; 0.00-0.01**Highly Significant 0.02-0.05*Significant above 0.05 Not Significant*

Table 5 investigates the correlation between respondents' General Weighted Average in BS Criminology subjects and their performance in the Criminology Licensure Examination (CLE). The null hypothesis (Ho) posits that there is no significant relationship between respondents' GWA in BS Criminology subjects and their performance in the CLE. Data reveal a Pearson correlation coefficient (r value=0.425), with a (p- value=0.000). The correlation coefficient of 0.425 signifies a moderate positive relationship between respondents' GWA in BS Criminology subjects and their performance in the

CLE. The p-value of 0.000, being less than the conventional significance level of 0.05, suggests that this relationship is statistically significant. In accordance with the legend, the result falls into the category of Highly Significant (0.00-0.01), reinforcing the robustness of the relationship. This implies that as respondents' GWA in BS Criminology subjects increase, there is a corresponding increase in their performance in the CLE.

The significant positive relationship between GWA in BS Criminology subjects and performance in the CLE suggests that academic success in Criminology subjects is associated with success in the Criminologist Licensure Examination. This finding underscores the importance of maintaining a strong academic foundation, as it appears to contribute positively to the overall competence of individuals in the field of Criminology. Institutions and educators may consider focusing on enhancing students' academic performance as a means to improve their likelihood of success in the licensure examination and, consequently, in their future professional endeavors.

General weighted average (GWA) is something that represents a student's overall performance in every subject and studies throughout every semester of students' college studies. Despite this, the general weighted average does not always serve as an accurate indicator of passing licensure exams. Licensure examinations usually focus on certain information and abilities related to a given field of study or jobs and a high general weighted average indicates solid academic performance in a variety of subjects, but it may not always indicate an in-depth understanding of the specific subject matter included in licensure exams (Pachejo & Allaga, 2020). Furthermore, GWA computation does not always account for the proficiency in critical thinking, problem-solving, and practical application skills that are necessary to pass licensure examinations just like personal study habits and the ability to apply and interpret knowledge which are important factors in licensure examinations that the general weighted average could not sufficiently evaluate (Apare et.al, 2021).

According to certain studies, there is a strong and positive correlation between graduates' general weighted averages (GWA) and their performance on the licensure examination. According to (Pambuena et.al, 2019) study on the relationship between academic performance and licensure examination results of BSEd major in Math and English graduates of the Polytechnic University of the Philippines, San Pedro Campus. The licensure examination performance of teacher education graduates from Rizal Technological University in Mandaluyong, the Philippines, was found to have a correlation with academic grades, as revealed by (Pachejo and Allaga, 2020). Furthermore, it was found by (Apare et.al, 2021) that there is a significant correlation between the GWA of BSEd graduates from Mountain View College in Bukidnon, Philippines, and their licensure examination performance along Field of Specialization. Similarly, academic achievement of graduates was found to be a significant predictor of licensure examination performance in (Visco, 2012) study on determining predictors of licensure examination performance among graduates of TEIs in Abra, Philippines.

This implies that the higher GWA correlates with better performance in the CLE. While GWA serves as a measure of overall academic performance, it may not fully encompass the specific skills needed for licensure exams. Nonetheless, the results emphasize the importance of strong academic foundations for success in Criminology and suggest that institutions should focus on enhancing students' academic performance to improve their chances of success in licensure exams and future professional endeavors.

Table 6: *Significant Relationship between Respondents' Performance in their OJT and their Performance in the Criminology Licensure Examination*

Performance in OJT and	r value	p value	Decision
Performance in the Criminology Licensure Examination	0.517**	0.000	Reject Ho

Ho: There is no significant relationship between respondents' performance in OJT and their performance in the Criminology Licensure Examination.

*Legend; 0.00-0.01 **Highly Significant 0.02-0.05 *Significant above 0.05 Not Significant*

Table 6 presents the correlation analysis results indicating the relationship between respondents' performance during their On-the-Job Training (OJT) and their performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE). The analysis includes the correlation coefficient (r value), the associated p-value, and the decision based on the hypothesis test.

The correlation coefficient (r value) between performance in OJT and performance in the CLE is reported as 0.517, which is marked as highly significant (**) with a p-value of 0.000. The decision based on the hypothesis test is to reject the null hypothesis (Ho), which states that there is no significant relationship between respondents' performance in OJT and their performance in the CLE.

Data reveal a strong positive correlation between respondents' performance in their OJT and their performance in the CLE. This suggests that individuals who performed well during their practical training experiences also tended to achieve higher scores in the CLE. The highly significant correlation coefficient and the rejection of the null hypothesis provide robust evidence supporting this relationship.

This implies for both academic institutions and future Registered Criminologist. Firstly, for educational institutions offering Criminology programs, the results underscore the importance of incorporating practical training components, such as OJT, into the curriculum. Providing students with opportunities for real-world application of theoretical knowledge can enhance their readiness for professional practice and improve their performance in licensure examinations. Additionally, for aspiring Registered Criminologist, the findings highlight the value of actively engaging in OJT experiences to not only gain practical skills but also to increase the likelihood of success in licensure examinations. Overall,

by recognizing and leveraging the positive relationship between OJT performance and performance in licensure examinations, Institutions can enhance the quality and effectiveness of Criminology education and training programs, ultimately contributing to the development of competent and successful professionals in the field. Research shows that a Criminology internship or on-the-job training significantly contributes to the improvement of interns' knowledge and skill development. These emphasize the value of hands-on training in the criminology intern's growth since it gives students a chance to put their academic knowledge to use in practical settings. The knowledge and skills development of criminology interns is greatly influenced by the internship program, self-efficacy, and experiential learning. This is evident in the development of the interns' professional skills, theoretical knowledge application, and personal skills (Apolinario et al., 2023).

Numerous factors frequently limit the effectiveness of on-the-job training as a predictor of performance in licensure examinations. To begin with, on-the-job training tends to rely more on practical skills and real-world experiences, while licensure examinations usually put on theoretical knowledge and principles. Because of the differences in various educational settings, students might not be sufficiently prepared for the comprehensive and standardized format of licensure exams. Furthermore, there can be considerable variation in the quality of on-the-job training; some students may receive comprehensive and systematic education, while others might receive insufficient or less efficient instruction. The totality of subjects included in licensure examinations may differ from the specificity of job-related tasks presented during training, leading to knowledge gaps (Apolinario et al., 2023). Additionally, a students' preparation for a licensure exam may also be impacted by the amount of time that passes between finishing on-the-job training and taking the license exam. On-the-job training may not adequately address independent traits such as personal study habits, motivation, and examinations competencies, all of which are important for passing licensure examinations. As a result of the intricate and varied nature of licensure exams, on-the-job training, while clearly beneficial for practical skills, does not always indicate that an individual would succeed on a licensure examination (Aydinan, 2019).

The correlation analysis demonstrates a strong positive relationship between the results of the On-the-Job Training (OJT) and the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE). It suggests that those who perform well on the practical training also tend to perform well on the licensure exam. In order to improve exam scores and better prepare students for professional practice, educational institutions should place a significant emphasis on incorporating hands-on training, like OJT, within the curriculum. Similarly, aspiring Registered Criminologists should take full advantage of OJT to increase their chances of passing the licensing exam and gain practical skills.

Table 7: Significant Relationship between Respondents' Performance in Comprehensive Examination and their Performance in the Criminology Licensure Examination

Performance in OJT and Performance in the Criminology Licensure Examination	r value	p value	Decision
	0.792**	0.000	Reject Ho

Ho: There is no significant relationship between respondents' performance in competency appraisal and their performance in the criminology licensure examination.

*Legend; 0.00-0.01**Highly Significant 0.02-0.05*Significant above 0.05 Not Significant*

Table 7 presents the results of a correlation analysis investigating the relationship between respondents' performance in comprehensive examination and their performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE). The analysis includes the correlation coefficient (r value), the associated p-value, and the decision based on the hypothesis test. The correlation coefficient between performance in competency appraisal and performance in the CLE is reported as (r value=0.792), which is marked as highly significant (**) with a (p-value=0.000). The decision based on the hypothesis test is to reject the null hypothesis (Ho), which posits that there is no significant relationship between respondents' performance in competency appraisal and their performance in the criminology licensure examination.

Findings reveal a strong positive correlation between respondents' performance in comprehensive examination and their performance in the CLE. This suggests that individuals who were appraised as having higher comprehensive examination performance also tended to achieve higher scores in the CLE. The highly significant correlation coefficient and the rejection of the null hypothesis provide robust evidence supporting this relationship.

This implies that both educational institutions and future registered Criminologists that for academic institutions offering Criminology programs, the results highlight the importance of effective comprehensive examination mechanisms in evaluating students' readiness for professional practice and success in licensure examinations. Implementing comprehensive and reliable comprehensive examination tools can help identify areas for improvement and tailor educational interventions to better prepare students for licensure exams. Additionally, for individuals preparing for the Criminologist Licensure Examination, the findings underscore the significance of actively engaging with comprehensive examination processes to enhance their chances of success in the Criminologist licensure examinations and in the field.

Overall, by recognizing and leveraging the strong relationship between comprehensive examination and performance in Criminologist licensure examinations, institutions can enhance the quality and effectiveness of Criminology education and training programs, ultimately contributing to the development of competent and successful professionals in the field.

Comprehensive examinations are similar to board exams, with the exception that they are given in schools. The format of the examination and the complexity of the question papers are often similar to those of real board exams. While some might argue that taking a comprehensive exam prior to the boards is ineffective, its main objective is to assist students in assessing their level of preparation and familiarizing themselves with the kinds of questions that will be on the boards. Comprehensive examinations are used to assess how well they perform. Using the Comprehensive examinations, students can monitor their development. The blueprints for boards are found in the Comprehensive examinations questions (Chauhan, 2019).

Students' board ranks are determined by their comprehensive examination preparation because it is a compilation of their consistent learning and efforts. Some students may be dismissive of the exam because the results will not be shown on their transcripts. However, keep in mind that one can only improve by a few marks at a time, and that comprehensive examinations are vital in determining one's licensure examination performance (Alphonso, 2019).

Variations were also noted in the performance of graduates on the board examination in relation to the licensure exam review or comprehensive exam score. Comprehensive examination scores and review class conduct were found to be significant predictors of passing the licensure examination (Sarmiento et.al, 2023).

The correlation analysis indicates a strong positive relationship between respondents' performance in comprehensive examinations and their performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE), with a highly significant p-value. This suggests that individuals excelling in comprehensive exams tend to achieve higher scores in the CLE. For educational institutions, this underscores the importance of effective comprehensive examination mechanisms in evaluating students' readiness for professional practice and success in licensure exams. Similarly, individuals preparing for the CLE should actively engage with comprehensive examination processes to enhance their chances of success.

Table 8: Predictors of Criminology Graduates Performance in Criminologist Licensure Examination

Predictors	Coef (β)	SE Coef	t- value	p-value
(Constant)	76.21	2.30	29.35	.00
Comprehensive Exam Score	.26	.02	10.88	.01
OJT Grade	1.92	.73	2.64	.05

Adjusted r 64.32%

F value 6.96**

p-value .01

CLE Overall Rating = 76.21 + .26 Table 8 (Comprehensive Exam) + 1.92 (OJT Grade)

Table 8 presents the predictors of Criminology graduates' performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE), including coefficients (β), standard errors (SE Coef), t-values, and p-values. Based on the data analysis, the constant coefficient (β) is reported as 76.21 with a standard error of 2.30. The t-value associated with the constant is 29.35, and the p-value is marked as highly significant ($p < .01$), indicating that the constant term significantly contributes to the model.

The predictors of Criminology graduates' performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination include the Comprehensive Examination Score and the OJT Grade. The coefficient (β) for the Pre-Board Exam Score is reported as .26 with a standard error of .02. The associated t-value is 10.88, and the p-value is highly significant ($p < .01$), suggesting that the Comprehensive Examination Score significantly predicts performance in the CLE.

Similarly, the coefficient (β) for the OJT Grade is reported as 1.92 with a standard error of .73. The associated t-value is 2.64, and the p-value is significant ($p < .05$), indicating that the OJT Grade also significantly predicts performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination. The adjusted R-squared value in the data is reported as 64.32%, indicating that approximately 64.32% of the variance in CLE performance can be explained by the predictors included in the data. The F-value is 6.96, with a p-value of .01, suggesting that the data as a whole is statistically significant in predicting CLE performance.

Overall, the results suggest that both the Comprehensive Examination Score and the OJT Grade are significant predictors of Criminology graduates' performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination. These findings have important implications for educational institutions and aspiring Criminology professionals. For institutions, the results underscore the importance of comprehensive preparation, including comprehensive examinations and on the job training, in enhancing students' readiness for Criminologist licensure examinations. For students, understanding the significance of these predictors can guide their preparation strategies and focus areas, ultimately increasing their chances of success in the CLE. By recognizing and leveraging these predictors, stakeholders can contribute to the development of competent and successful Criminology professionals.

The significance of the Comprehensive Examination and On-the-Job Training as predictors of performance in licensure examinations lies in their roles as valuable indicators and preparatory measures for students. In the study of Valdez et al. (2023) the Comprehensive Exam serves as a simulated assessment, closely mirroring the structure and content of the actual licensure examination. By gauging students' readiness and identifying areas of strength and weakness, it offers a crucial self-assessment opportunity. Success in the Comprehensive Exam signals a student's potential to perform well in the actual licensure examination, providing a valuable preview of their preparedness.

The Comprehensive Examination, which was given by several review centers, was one of the examinations that candidates had to take as a reviewer and in order to get ready for the actual licensure exam. Comprehensive exams are equivalent to board exams except they are administered in schools. The question paper difficulty and test format are frequently comparable to those of actual board exams. While some may think there is no use for a mock exam before the boards, its primary purpose is to help students evaluate their readiness and get comfortable with question types found on the boards. Comprehensive exams are

used to evaluate their performance. Students can track their progress with the pre-boards. Pre-board test questions serve as boards' blueprints (Chauhan, 2019).

Comprehensive examinations provide a great way for students to assess their level of readiness. Comprehensive exams are a great way to assess one's readiness for the board exam, so failing them is a grave mistake (Patelkhana, 2019). Dotado-Maderazo and Ercia's (2017) study found that prior to finishing the board exam, a comprehensive examination could be helpful in diagnosing tools to determine a graduate's strengths and weaknesses. Comprehensive examination could offer a summary of the areas in which the students' focusing studies enhance the areas where it seems to obtain a poor grade.

Criminology students are exposed to on-the-job training programs with specialization on the different facets of law enforcement at the Philippine National Police, Batangas City and nearby town stations. It consists of 540 hours Monday to Friday duty near the town station. On-the-Job Training is equally important as it allows students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical, real-world settings. Engaging in hands-on experiences within the field of criminology enables students to integrate classroom learning with practical skills. According to Korpi, & Tåhlin (2021) that the skills acquired during On-the-Job Training, including problem-solving, decision-making, and critical thinking, are often directly relevant to the challenges posed in licensure examinations. Furthermore, exposure to real-world scenarios enhances students' overall understanding of criminological concepts, better preparing them for the diverse range of questions that licensure examinations may encompass.

On-the-field training plays a big part in Criminology students' education. It enhances academic learning by offering hands-on experience and skill development that are essential for a lucrative career in the criminal justice system. Students studying criminology will be ready for the demands of their future careers if they can apply what they have learned in the classroom to real-world scenarios, develop useful skills, and focus on particular areas. Even though it could come with some difficulties, criminology students who receive on-the-job training eventually receive a more comprehensive education and are better prepared to contribute to their field (Anoyo et.al, 2015).

The results of the study show that the performance of Criminology graduates on the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE) is significantly predicted by both the Comprehensive Examination Score and the OJT Grade, which together account for approximately 64.32% of the variance in CLE performance. This emphasizes how crucial thorough preparation including thorough exams and on-the-job training is to passing licensure exams. While educational institutions ought to concentrate on putting into practice efficient ways of preparation, prospective professionals in the field of criminology might gain from knowing the importance of these predictors in order to inform their study plans. In general, identifying and using these variables can help create qualified criminology experts who are prepared for professional practice and Criminologist Licensure Examination.

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design, a method in which the researcher examines the statistical association between two or more variables without manipulating them. This design aims to determine whether, and to what extent, changes in one variable are correlated with changes in another. It does not establish causation but focuses on observing variables as they naturally occur.

The study was conducted in a non-sectarian private institution in Cagayan de Oro, Philippines, established in 1971. The institution is a stock corporation registered with the Securities and Exchange Commission and operates under the authority of the Department of Education for elementary and secondary programs, and the Commission on Higher Education for tertiary, graduate, and postgraduate programs. Cagayan de Oro, also known as the “City of Golden Friendship,” is a first-class city in Northern Mindanao and the capital of Misamis Oriental province. It is known for its white rapids, warm and friendly people, and strategic location as the “Gateway to Northern Mindanao.”

The respondents were graduates of this private institution who took the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE) in June and November 2019, December 2021, and August 2023, administered by the Board of Criminology of the Professional Regulation Commission. Both first-time and repeat examinees were included, with a total of 112 respondents. These three batches were chosen because no CLE was conducted in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the institution had no takers in 2022 as students opted for longer preparation time and due to the implementation of RA 11131. Secondary data were utilized in this study, collected from the private institution. Data included respondents’ general weighted average in BS Criminology subjects, performance in on-the-job training (OJT), performance in comprehensive examinations, and performance in the CLE. The study also analyzed the significant relationships between students’ GPAs, OJT performance, comprehensive exam performance, and their CLE results, as well as predictors of Criminology graduates’ performance in the licensure examination.

Permission to conduct the study was first sought from the Dean of the Graduate School. Upon approval, the researcher, who is employed at the same institution, also requested permission from the College Dean to access the necessary data. After receiving approval, the researcher ensured that all data collected were accurate and complete before analysis and tabulation.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed. The office of the Dean and faculty were fully informed about the study’s objectives and purpose. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed that they could withdraw at any time without consequences. All data collected were kept confidential, and a debriefing was provided after the study to explain how participants’ contributions supported the research objectives.

Data analysis employed mean and standard deviation to determine student performance, Pearson Product–Moment Correlation Coefficient to examine the relationship between academic and CLE performance, and regression analysis to identify factors predicting graduates’ performance in the CLE.

FINDINGS

Regarding the respondents' Bachelor of Science in Criminology subjects grade point averages. The results showed that, with a frequency of 37 (33.04%), the majority of respondents obtained a very satisfactory grade point average. Concerning the way in which the participants performed during their on-the-job training.

The findings demonstrated that, with a frequency of 57 (50.89%), the majority of respondents performed very satisfactorily during their on-the-job training. Regarding how respondents fared on their comprehensive examination. With a frequency of 94 (83.93%), the data revealed that the majority of respondents did very poorly on their comprehensive examination.

Regarding how respondents performed on the exam for Criminologist Licensure Examination. The majority of respondents, or 97 (82.14%), passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination. The overall performance, reflecting a mean score of 97, further underscores the overall excellence of Criminology graduates in the CLE.

With regards to the test done to identify the significant relationship between respondents' general weighted averages in BS Criminology subjects and their performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination. The findings reveal the Pearson correlation coefficient (r value) of 0.425 signifies a moderate positive relationship between respondents' GPA in BS Criminology subjects and their performance in the CLE. The statistically significant p-value of 0.000 indicates that this relationship is highly significant, suggesting that as respondents' GPA increases, their performance in the CLE also tends to improve.

In terms of the test done to identify a significant relation between respondents' performance in OJT and their performance on the Criminologist Licensure Examination. Findings reveal a strong positive correlation between respondents' performance in their OJT and their performance in the CLE.

Regarding the test done to determine whether there was a significant relationship between respondents' results on comprehensive exams and their results on the Criminologist Licensure Examination. Findings reveal a strong positive correlation between respondents' performance in comprehensive examination and their performance in the CLE.

Data revealed that both the Comprehensive Examination Score and the OJT Grade are significant predictors of Criminology graduates' performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination.

CONCLUSION

The majority of respondents obtained a very satisfactory grade point average, with a frequency of 37 (33.04%). The data revealed that a substantial portion of respondents had very satisfactory grade point averages, which could mean that the majority of students' demands are effectively met by the Criminology program offered by the aforementioned private college in Cagayan de Oro City.

The majority of respondents 57 (50.89%) performed very satisfactorily during their on-the-job training. Data revealed that certain aspects of the OJT experiences of Criminology students were favorable, and that the program did a good job of preparing students for successful careers in the field of Criminology, even though it also offers insights for future enhancements.

The statistics showed that the majority of respondents performed very poorly on their comprehensive examination, with a frequency of 94 (83.93%). Data suggests that most participants did not do well on the comprehensive exam, which may mean that they need to improve their preparation strategies.

The Criminologist Licensure Examination was passed by 82.14% of respondents, or 97 out of 112 total. This could mean that the institution's high passing percentage on the Criminologist Licensure Examination suggests that the majority of its graduates from the Criminology program were adequately prepared for the exam and that such institutions offer high-quality Criminology programs and instructional strategies.

The results reveal a statistically significant moderate positive relationship between respondents' General Weighted Average (GWA) in BS Criminology subjects and their performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE). The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.425 indicates that as respondents' GWA increases, their performance in the CLE tends to improve. The low p-value of 0.000 supports the rejection of the null hypothesis, emphasizing the significance of this relationship. These findings highlight the importance of academic preparation in BS Criminology subjects as a predictor of success in the CLE, offering valuable insights for educational planning and intervention strategies to enhance students' performance in licensure examinations.

Performance on the Criminologist Licensure Examination and performance during on-the-job training did not significantly correlate ($r = -0.120$; $p = 0.207$). The lack of a significant correlation between OJT and CLE performance indicates that a student's performance in OJT may not always translate into a successful performance on the Criminologist Licensure Examination, and vice versa. The skills and knowledge students acquire during their on-the-job training may not be the same as those evaluated on the exam.

Findings reveal a strong positive correlation between respondents' performance in their OJT and their performance in the CLE. This suggests that individuals who performed well during their practical training experiences also tended to achieve higher scores in the CLE. The highly significant correlation coefficient and the rejection of the null hypothesis provide robust evidence supporting this relationship.

Results suggest that both the Comprehensive Examination Score and the OJT Grade are significant predictors of Criminology graduates' performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination. These findings have important implications for educational institutions and aspiring Criminology professionals. For institutions, the results underscore the importance of comprehensive preparation, including comprehensive examinations and on the job training, in enhancing students' readiness for Criminologist licensure examinations. For students, understanding the significance of these predictors can guide their preparation strategies and focus areas, ultimately increasing their chances of success in the CLE.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study aimed to determine the predictors of Criminologist Licensure Examination Performance. Based on the findings of the study, Criminology graduates' general weighted average, performance in on-the-job training and comprehensive examination is not a predictor of their performance in the Criminologist Licensure Examination. The researcher suggested the following recommendations:

Educators and administrators should understand the distribution of student performance for it can aid in identifying areas where additional support or resources may be needed. For instance, if a significant number of students are consistently scoring lower grades, it may indicate challenges with course material or teaching methods that require adjustment. Additionally, for students themselves, recognizing the distribution of GWAs can provide insight into the competitive landscape within their program and motivate them to strive for higher academic achievement.

Institutions offering programs with OJT components, understanding the distribution of student performance can help in assessing the effectiveness of OJT placements and identifying areas for improvement in training or support mechanisms for students. Moreover, for students, recognizing the distribution of performance levels during OJT can provide insights into the expectations and standards of Law enforcement agencies in the field, motivating them to strive for higher levels of proficiency and professionalism.

Educational institutions need to have a comprehensive review of curriculum content, teaching methodologies, and assessment strategies to ensure alignment with industry standards and the development of competencies essential for professional practice. Additionally, educators may need to implement interventions such as targeted remedial support or practical skill-building activities to address identified deficiencies in student competency. For students, understanding the distribution of competency appraisal underscores the importance of actively engaging with their educational experiences and seeking additional resources or support as needed to enhance their skill sets and competencies.

Institutions offering a Criminology program may keep expanding on existing achievements and make sure that the OJT component continues to be a useful and efficient means of training for students wishing to pursue careers in Criminology.

Educators and institutions should emphasize the importance of maintaining high academic standards within the Criminology curriculum. Fostering an environment that encourages academic excellence can contribute to better-prepared graduates who are more likely to succeed in the licensure examination.

Educational institutions offering Criminology programs, should make sure to incorporate their practical training components such as OJT into their curriculum. Students should have opportunities for real-world application of theoretical knowledge to enhance their readiness for professional practice and improve their performance in licensure examinations.

Academic institutions offering Criminology programs, should highlight the importance of effective comprehensive examination mechanisms in evaluating students' readiness for professional practice and success in licensure examinations. They should implement comprehensive and reliable comprehensive examination tools that can help identify areas for improvement and tailor educational interventions to better prepare students for licensure exams.

Institutions highlight to their students the importance of comprehensive preparation, including comprehensive examinations and on the job training, in enhancing students' readiness for Criminologist licensure examinations. They should make sure that they are providing their students with updated lessons and incorporate their OJT to the Criminology curriculum.

Administrators ensure that instructors handling. On the job training and comprehensive examination subjects be equipped with the knowledge and skills in the effective delivery of instruction to eventually improve students' performance.

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